

Trifluoro- β -diketonates of Tin(IV)

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Adducts and substituted products of tin tetrachloride and monoorganotin trichloride with unsymmetrical trifluoro- β -diketonates, $\text{CF}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{COR}$ (LH) (R = Me, Et, i-Pr and Ph) have been prepared and characterised. Ir spectra of adducts, $\text{SnCl}_4\cdot\text{LH}$ are consistent with the enolic form of the chelating diketone leading to an octahedral structure. X-ray crystal and molecular structure of complex, $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{CF}_3\text{COCHCOR})_2$ confirms *cis-trans-cis* stereochemistry. ^1H nmr spectra suggest these to be fluxional in solution. For organotin complexes, only tentative structures could be proposed from the limited spectral data.

Metal β -diketonates¹ have been a subject of renewed interest because these happen to be accessible and soluble metalloorganic compounds for application as essential component for preparing heterometallic aggregates². The aggregates function as intermediate on the molecular route in sol-gel process for multicomponent oxides. In view of the difficult synthesis of tin alkoxide as precursor for conducting indium tin oxide (ITO)³ and increased organic properties in metal fluoro- β -diketonates, we have synthesised and characterised a few tin(IV) fluoro- β -diketonates which may find applications in the production of the solid state materials based on tin.

Results and Discussion

Trifluoro- β -diketonates, $\text{CF}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{COR}$ with tin tetrachloride form adducts, $\text{SnCl}_4\cdot\text{LH}$ (1) in chloroform at 0°, whereas bis-derivatives, $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{L})_2$ (2) are the final product from the reaction under

refluxing conditions. Monoorganotin(IV) derivatives (3–5) are obtainable by the reaction of monoorganotin(IV) chloride with sodium salt of the ketones,

$$n = 1-3$$

(R = Me, Et, i-Pr and Ph)

All these complexes are distillable liquids or crystallisable solids, soluble in common organic solvents. Molecular weight and conductance data in the ionising solvent acetonitrile show that all the complexes behave as monomeric nonelectrolytes. Physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL and IMPORTANT IR AND NMR DATA OF TIN COMPLEXES OF $\text{CF}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{COR}$

Compd. no*	Compd.	M p (°C) B.p. (°C/mm)	Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis%		ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)					$^1\text{H}_{\text{nmr}}$	
				Sn	Cl	(OH)	...	Sn-C	Sn-O	Sn-Cl	CH	Me
1a	$\text{SnCl}_4\cdot\text{LH}$ (R = Me)		396 (414)	28.6 (28.7)	34.7 (34.3)	3 312b	1 592s	1 522s	444s	352s 340s	6.12	2.04 2.49
	$\text{SnCl}_4\cdot\text{LH}$ (R = i-Pr)		433 (442)	26.7 (26.7)	31.7 (32.1)	3 400b	1 595s	1 530s	448s	350s 342s	6.02	1 24 ^a
2a	$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{L})_2$ (R = Me)		526 (496)	24.6 (24.9)	14.9 (14.3)		1 596s	1 525s	440s	360s 350w	5.90	2.39 2.48

Table-1 (Contd.)

2b	SnCl ₂ (L) ₂ (R = <i>i</i> -Pr)	537 (551)	20.4 (21.0)	11.9 (12.9)	1 601s	1 526s	432s	360s 340s	—	—	
2c	SnCl ₂ (L) ₂ (R = Ph)	180	—	19.5 (19.1)	1 591s	1 530s	430s	350 335w	6.13	—	
3a	BuSnCl ₂ (L) (R = Me)	410 (399)	29.6 (29.7)	17.5 (17.8)	1 601s	1 524s	582s	422s	317s 362w	6.00 2.30	
3b	BuSnCl ₂ (L) (R = Et)	—	28.4 (28.7)	17.0 (17.2)	1 608s	1 524s	583s	423s	322s 362w	—	
4a	BuSnCl(L) ₂ (R = Me)	118/0.9 (517)	525 (517)	23.9 (23.9)	6.9 (7.1)	1 610s	1 525s	585s	422s	320s 5.94	2.33
4b	BuSnCl(L) ₂ (R = <i>i</i> -Pr)	125/0.1	—	21.1 (20.7)	5.8 (6.2)	1 612s	1 530s	582s	422s	320s	—
5a	BuSn(L) ₃ (R = Me)	617 (624)	18.2 (18.9)	—	1 615s	1 530s	582s	425s	—	5.95	2.32
5b	PhSn(L) ₃ (R = Ph)	—	—	14.2 (14.1)	—	1 595s	1 543s	584s	425s	—	—

***1**, **3** Colourless liquid; **2a**, **2b** light brown viscous liquid, **2c** white solids, **4**, **5** light yellow liquid. ^a Centre of the quartet Molar conductance (Λ_m) in MeCN at 25° for **1a** and **1b**, 3–6, and for **2a** and **2b** 1–2 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ of $10^{-3} M$ solution ¹³C nmr (δ) for **3a**, (Me)C, 201.24; (CF₃)C, 170.20; CH, 123.10; CF₃ 127.44; Me, 31.21, **4a** (Me)C, 204.00; (CF₃)C, 174.00; CH, 118.14, CF₃, 131.24, Me, 33.10; **5a** (Me)C, 202.10; (CF₃)C, 170.60; CH, 123.15; CF₃ 127.40, Me, 31.14, ¹H nmr or organo-group attached to tin in 3–5 displayed multiplet at δ 0.9–2.8 for *n*-Bu and 7.1–8.0 for Ph

For the adducts **1**, the ir spectra show a broad band at 3 300–3 400 cm^{-1} (Table 1) assignable to ν_{OH} vibration mode revealing that the enolic form of the ligand is essentially coordinating to tin. The presence of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ at lower frequencies in the region 1 592–1 595 cm^{-1} (in comparison to the free trifluoro- β -diketones which absorb at 1 650–1 720 cm^{-1}) indicates bidentately bonded ligand-pattern in the solid state. The far-infrared region, 500–200 cm^{-1} contains contributions from both (Sn–O) and (Sn–Cl) stretchings. While $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{O}}$ band occurs at 445–500 cm^{-1} (Ref. 4), two bands in the region 340–352 cm^{-1} may arise due to (Sn–Cl) stretchings. All these observations are consistent with the adducts having structure shown in Fig 1. Interestingly, ¹H nmr spectrum of an adduct (**1a**) at 24° displays two signals for methyl protons and a singlet for methine proton. Also, in case of **1b**, two sets of doublets due to *gem*-dimethyl protons are observed. The chemical shift of one in the set of two is close to the ligand and the other one relatively downfield. This spectral feature may be accounted in terms of the presence of dissociative equilibrium in solution (Fig. 1) where the ligand jumps between the free and the complex site.

In bis-substituted complexes **2**, the ir spectra display a band around 420–450 cm^{-1} assignable to

$\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{O}}$ mode. The chelating characteristic absorption due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and the presence of two peaks due

Fig 1.

to $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{Cl}}$ vibrations around 320 and 350 cm^{-1} suggest that these are *cis*-octahedral in the solid state. The ortep plot on the X-ray and molecular structure (Fig. 2) of **2c** confirms this and reveal a

Fig. 2. Molecular structure of SnCl₂(CF₃COCHCOPh)₂ (**2c**).

Fig. 3.

cis-trans-cis stereochemistry. Notably this is the first structural information on an unsymmetrical β -diketonate. As the R values are still not within limits, the data require refinement. We, therefore, defer any detailed discussion on it.

Importantly, in ^1H nmr spectrum of complex **2a**, two methyl signals are observed at δ 2.39 and 2.48 and a singlet for the methine proton at δ 5.90 at 24° . This can be rationalised presuming that the complex is *cis*-octahedral and in solution maintains a *cis-cis-cis* configuration⁵ (Fig. 3).

At higher temperature (64°), both the methyl signals coalesced to one single line suggesting an intramolecular exchange process. Amongst the several possibilities, the coalescence could arise through enantiomerisation by twisting through a C_3 axis. It may or may not involve isomerisation. Only a detailed kinetic analysis of DNMR pattern can give mechanistic information.

Usually the final products formed by the reaction of tin tetrachloride with trifluoro- β -diketonates remains the bis-complex (**2**). However, by using the more reactive sodium salt of the ligand, the tris, $\text{SnCl}(\text{CF}_3\text{COCHCOMe})_3$, and tetrakis, $\text{Sn}(\text{CF}_3\text{COCHCOMe})_4$ have also been synthesised. These derivatives are very unstable and could not be well characterised. The infrared spectral data suggest that in these derivatives, all the ligands are not bonded bidentately but some of them are bonded through enolic oxygen. This is inferred from the appearance of two bands due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ one at a higher frequency ($\sim 1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the other in the chelating region ($\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$). It has not been possible to get any reproducible nmr data due to decomposition of these two complexes in solution.

The infrared spectra of monoorganotin(IV) monobis- and tris-complexes (**3–5**, Table 1) also do

not show any important absorption above 1650 cm^{-1} . This suggests that trifluoro- β -diketonate moiety are coordinated through both the oxygen atoms to tin. The absorptions arising due to $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{C}}$, $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{Cl}}$ vibrations are listed in the table. The dichloro complexes (**3**) display two absorptions due to tin-chlorine vibrations revealing *cis*-orientation for the chlorines. While ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra of all these three systems do not throw any light on the molecular structure, ^{119}Sn data is expected to be diagnostic. For **3a** the presence of ^{119}Sn resonance line at -117.7 ppm provides a strong evidence for five-coordination around tin. This may be considered to possess a trigonal bipyramidal structure.

The monochloro (**4**) and tris (**5**) complexes have much lower symmetry than **2**. There is a possibility of several isomers around any geometrical configuration. For example, ^{19}F nmr spectra of **4a** from $+24$ to -60° give single line at 74.8 ppm which definitely suggest rapid exchange process in solution. A similar nmr spectrum of **5a** shows three signals at 74.5 , 75.8 and 82.4 ppm at room temperature. In summary with the limited spectral data it is not possible to assign any probable geometry for complexes **4** and **5**.

Experimental

Precaution was taken to exclude moisture throughout the experimental work. Solvents were dried by standard literature procedures. Trifluoro- β -diketonates were prepared by Claisen condensation method⁶. Sodium salts of these were made by the addition of a benzene solution of the ligand to sodium hydride (1 : 2 molar ratio) suspended in benzene cooled at 0° and under nitrogen atmosphere. After stirring for 3 h, the separated sodium salt was washed with benzene several times and dried at $50^\circ/0.1\text{ mm}$ for 5 h. Tin tetrachloride (114°), n-butyltin(IV) trichloride ($93^\circ/10\text{ mm}$) and phenyltin

trichloride (96–97°/1 mm) were distilled before use. For preparation of the complexes 1–5 (Table 1), 3–6 mmol of the reactants were taken.

Tin was estimated as SnO₂ and chlorine as silver chloride (gravimetrically). Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically in benzene. Conductance was determined by a bridge (L-370873, Cambridge Instrument) in acetonitrile. IR spectra (neat/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer using CsI plates. Nmr spectra (¹H, ¹³C, ¹¹⁹Sn and ¹⁹F) were recorded on a JEOL FX 90 Q spectrometer in CDCl₃, CCl₄ or CD₃CN (TMS as internal standard for ¹H and ¹³C, CFCl₃ for ¹⁹F and BuSnCl₃ as external reference for ¹¹⁹Sn).

Preparation of adducts 1 : A chloroform solution (~10 ml) of trifluoro-β-diketone was added dropwise into a stirred chloroform solution (~15 ml) of tin tetrachloride at ~ 0° in equimolar ratio. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4–5 h. The volatile materials were removed under reduced pressure and the resulting viscous liquid was dried at 30°/0.1 mm for 4 h (yield 96–98%).

Preparation of bis-complexes 2 : To a stirred solution of tin tetrachloride in chloroform (~15 ml), the double stoichiometric amount of trifluoro-β-diketone in chloroform (~10 ml) was added at room temperature. The contents were refluxed for ~ 48 h till the evolution of HCl gas was ceased. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting viscous liquid and solid products were dried under reduced pressure at 30°/0.1 mm for ~ 4 h (yield 95–98%).

Preparation of organotin complexes 3–5 : Organotin(IV) trichloride dissolved in benzene (~15 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of sodium salt of trifluoro-β-diketone in benzene (~20 ml). Stoichiometry taken were 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3. The reaction mixture was stirred for ~ 4 h at 30°. Separated sodium chloride was filtered out and the volatile materials from the filtrate evaporated under reduced pressure. The isolated products were dried at 38°/0.1 mm for ~ 5 h (yield 90–95%).

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